

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Review of Herbal Drugs Used in The Treatment of Skin Disorder

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 16 Dec. 2024

Keywords:

Botanicals, Phytochemicals, Herbal remedies, Traditional medicine, Natural products, Herbal supplements, Plant extracts, Herbal preparations, Herbal medicine, Herbal formulations Cardiovascular diseases, Cancer, Diabetes, Arthritis, Respiratory diseases, Digestive disorders, Neurological disorders, Dermatological conditions Infectious diseases, Autoimmune diseases.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14499152

ABSTRACT

Herbal drugs have long been utilized in the treatment of skin disorders, offering natural alternatives to conventional therapies. With their anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and wound-healing properties, many plant-based remedies show promise for managing conditions such as acne, eczema, psoriasis, and fungal infections. This review explores the therapeutic potential of various herbs and their active constituents, highlighting their mechanisms of action and clinical applications. Despite their benefits, the use of herbal drugs in dermatology requires careful consideration of safety, efficacy, and possible side effects, as well as the quality of herbal products. The need for further research and clinical trials is emphasized to establish standardized dosages, ensure therapeutic efficacy, and minimize risks. While herbal remedies can complement traditional treatments, their integration into clinical practice should be guided by healthcare professionals to optimize patient outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal drugs, derived from plants, have been integral to traditional medicine systems worldwide for centuries, offering remedies for various ailments. These natural compounds contain

bioactive ingredients that can influence physiological processes in the human body. However, their efficacy and safety profiles vary widely, making their use a subject of ongoing research and debate. Historically, herbal

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

medicines have been utilized to treat a myriad of diseases. For instance, in traditional Chinese medicine (TCM), herbs like ginseng, ginger, and ginkgo biloba have been employed to enhance vitality, alleviate digestive issues, and improve cognitive function, respectively. Similarly, Ayurveda, the ancient Indian healing system, relies on herbs such as turmeric, neem, and Ashwagandha to address conditions ranging from inflammation and skin disorders to stress and anxiety. In contemporary times, herbal drugs continue to play a significant role in complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) practices. They are often perceived as natural alternatives to conventional pharmaceuticals, appealing to individuals seeking gentler treatment options with potentially fewer side effects. For instance, herbal supplements like St. John's wort are widely used for managing mild to moderate depression, while Echinacea is popularly consumed to bolster the immune system and ward off infections. However, despite their popularity and perceived benefits, herbal drugs pose several challenges. Firstly, the variability in composition and potency of plant-derived compounds can lead to inconsistent therapeutic outcomes and interactions with other medications. Moreover, the lack of standardized manufacturing processes and quality control measures raises concerns regarding product purity and safety. Additionally, while some herbal remedies have demonstrated promising effects in clinical studies, others lack robust scientific evidence to support their efficacy or safety. Furthermore, the limited regulation of herbal products in many countries contributes to the proliferation of adulterated or mislabelled supplements, posing risks to consumers. In conclusion, herbal drugs offer a diverse array of therapeutic potentials and have been utilized for centuries to treat various diseases. However, their efficacy, safety, and regulatory oversight remain subjects of ongoing scrutiny and investigation. As

research advances and our understanding of herbal medicine deepens, integrating evidence-based approaches with traditional wisdom will be crucial in harnessing the full potential of herbal drugs for improving human health and well-being

History

Herbal drugs, also known as botanical medicines or phytomedicines, have a long and diverse history deeply intertwined with human civilization and the treatment of diseases. Dating back thousands of years, various cultures across the globe have utilized plants and herbs for medicinal purposes. From traditional Chinese medicine to Ayurveda in India, herbal remedies have been integral to healthcare practices worldwide. The use of herbal drugs can be traced to ancient civilizations such as the Sumerians, Egyptians, Greeks, and Romans. They recognized the therapeutic properties of plants and developed extensive pharmacopeia containing herbal remedies for treating a wide range of ailments. For instance, the Ebers Papyrus, an ancient Egyptian medical document dating back to around 1550 BCE, contains references to numerous herbal preparations for treating conditions like gastrointestinal disorders, infections, and skin diseases. In traditional Chinese medicine (TCM), herbal drugs are often prescribed in combination with other therapies such as acupuncture and qigong to restore balance and harmony within the body. Chinese Materia medica lists thousands of medicinal substances, primarily derived from plants, which are used to treat various diseases and promote health. Similarly, in Ayurveda, the traditional medicine system of India, herbal drugs play a central role in promoting holistic well-being. Ayurveda texts describe the properties and uses of hundreds of herbs, minerals, and animal products for treating physical ailments, and mental disorders, and promoting longevity. Throughout history, herbal medicine has evolved alongside advancements in scientific understanding and medical practices.

While some herbal remedies have stood the test of time and gained recognition for their efficacy, others have been discarded or refined based on empirical evidence and clinical research. In recent decades, there has been a resurgence of interest in herbal drugs as people seek alternative and complementary approaches to healthcare. Scientific studies have explored the pharmacological effects, safety, and efficacy of various botanical medicines, leading to the development of standardized herbal preparations and supplements. However, challenges persist in the integration of herbal medicine into modern

healthcare systems. Issues such as standardization of herbal products, quality control, herb-drug interactions, and lack of regulation pose concerns for both healthcare professionals and consumers. Despite these challenges, herbal medicine continues to be an important aspect of healthcare, providing alternative options for disease prevention and management. With ongoing research and collaboration between traditional knowledge systems and modern science, the potential of herbal drugs to address global health challenges remains promising.

Anatomy Of Skin

The skin is the largest organ of the human body, covering an average surface area of about 2 square meters (21.5 square feet) in adults. It serves several important functions, including protection, temperature regulation, sensory perception, and synthesis of vitamin D.

The skin is composed of three layers: the epidermis, dermis, and hypodermis.

1. Epidermis: This is the outermost layer of the skin, which is continuously being shed and replaced. It consists of several layers of dead keratinized cells that provide a protective barrier against the external environment. The outermost layer of the epidermis is the stratum corneum, which is the waterproof barrier that prevents water loss from the body.

2. Dermis: The dermis lies beneath the epidermis and is a thick layer of connective tissue that

provides support, nutrition, and elasticity to the skin. It contains blood vessels, sweat glands, hair follicles, and nerve endings. The dermis is also rich in collagen and elastin, which give the skin its strength and elasticity.

3. Hypodermis: The hypodermis is the deepest layer of the skin, which is composed of fatty tissue and connective tissue. It provides insulation, cushioning, and energy storage for the body.

The skin also contains several types of cells, including melanocytes, which produce melanin, the pigment that gives skin its colour. Melanin helps protect the skin from harmful UV radiation by absorbing and scattering it.

Common Skin Problems And Treatment

Common skin problems that herbal drugs may help treat include:

1. **Acne:** Herbal Remedies Such As Tea Tree Oil, Aloe Vera, And Green Tea Extract May Help Reduce Inflammation And Fight Acne-Causing Bacteria.
2. **Eczema:** Herbs Like Calendula, Chamomile, And Licorice Root Can Soothe Inflammation And Relieve Itching Associated With Eczema.
3. **Psoriasis:** Certain Herbs Like Turmeric, Oregon Grape, And Aloe Vera May Help Reduce The Symptoms Of Psoriasis, Such As Redness And Scaling.
4. **Rosecea:** Herbs Such As Extract, Liquorice Root, And Feverfew Have Anti-Inflammatory Properties That Can Help Alleviate Symptoms Of Rosacea, Including Redness And Flushing.
5. **Dry Skin:** Herbal Moisturizers Containing Ingredients Like Shea Butter, Coconut Oil, And Olive Oil Can Hydrate And Nourish Dry Skin.
6. **Wrinkles:** Herbal Remedies Like Rosehip Oil, Aloe Vera, And Ginseng May Help Reduce The Appearance Of Wrinkles And Improve Skin Elasticity.
7. **Sunburn:** Aloe Vera Gel Is Widely Used To Soothe Sunburned Skin Due to its cooling and anti-inflammatory properties.

It's important to note that while herbal remedies can be effective for some people, they may not work for everyone, and it's essential to consult with a healthcare professional before starting any herbal treatment regimen, especially if you have underlying health conditions or are taking medications. Additionally, herbal products can sometimes cause allergic reactions or interact with other medications, so it's crucial to use them with caution and under supervision.

There are several herbal drugs that have been traditionally used in the treatment of skin disorders examples:

Biological Source: *Allium sativum* (Garlic plant)
Chemical Source: Allicin (a sulfur compound) and other organosulfur compounds

1. Aloe Vera (*Aloe Barbadosis*): This plant is widely used for its soothing and healing properties. It's often used to treat sunburns, cuts, and other skin irritations.

2. Neem (*Azadirachta Indica*): Neem has anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antifungal properties. It's used to treat acne, eczema, and other skin conditions.

3. Turmeric (*Curcuma Longa*): Turmeric contains curcumin, which has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. It's often used to treat skin conditions like psoriasis and eczema.

4. Tea Tree Oil (*Melaleuca Alternifolia*): This oil has antimicrobial properties and is often used to treat acne and other skin infections.

5. Licorice Root (*Glycyrrhiza Glabra*): Licorice root has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. It's often used to treat skin conditions like eczema and psoriasis.

6. Calendula (*Calendula Officinalis*): Calendula has anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties. It's often used to treat skin irritations, wounds, and burns.

7. Chamomile (*Matricaria Chamomilla*): Chamomile has anti-inflammatory and soothing properties. It's often used to treat skin irritations and conditions like eczema.

8. Green Tea (*Camellia Sinensis*): Green tea contains antioxidants and has been shown to have skin-protective effects. It's often used to treat skin conditions like psoriasis and eczema.

Garlic:

Uses:

1. Culinary: Flavoring and seasoning in various dishes

2. Medicinal:

1. Antibacterial, antiviral, and antifungal properties
2. Cardiovascular health: lowers cholesterol and blood pressure
3. Immune system support
4. Anticancer properties
2. and fungicide

Turmeric:

3. Pharmaceutical: Raw material for the production of allicin and other garlic-derived drugs

4. Traditional Medicine:

1. Treatment of various ailments, such as colds, fever, and digestive issues

5. Agricultural:

1. Natural pest repellent

Biological source

1. Curcuma longa (Turmeric plant)

Medicinal Uses:

1. Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties
2. Pain relief and wound healing
3. Digestive aid and liver protection
4. Antiseptic and antibacterial properties
5. Cancer prevention and treatment

Chemical Source:

1. Curcumin (a polyphenolic compound) and other curcuminoids

Ginger:

Chemical Source :

1. Gingerol and shogaol (phenolic compounds)
2. Volatile oils like zingiberene, bisabolol, and gingerene
3. Resin and starch

Biological Name : Zingiber officinale

Family : Zingiberaceae (Ginger family)

2. Volatile oils like turmerone, atlantone, and zingiberene

Morphology:

1. Rhizome (underground stem) with yellow-orange color
2. Branched and finger-like projections
3. Waxy and smooth skin
4. Internally, it has a yellow-orange, juicy, and fibrous pulp
5. Leaves are long, narrow, and pointed
6. Flowers are yellowish-white and arranged in a spike

Morphology :

1. Rhizome (underground stem) with a thick, rough, and fibrous skin
2. Internally, it has a juicy and fibrous pulp
3. Leaves are long, narrow, and pointed
4. Flowers are yellowish-green and arranged in a spike
5. Fruits are small, capsular, and contain black seeds

Ginger Uses

1. Better Digestion. If you're having problems with indigestion, ginger can help speed up the digestion process and empty your stomach more quickly.
2. Improves Immunity.

3. Alleviates PMS Symptoms.
4. Relieves Nausea and Upset Stomach.
5. May Help With Cancer.
6. Reduces Pain.
7. Healthier Skin. Weight Loss Aid.

Medicinal Uses (of antifungal agents):

- a. Treatment of fungal infections, including ringworm
- b. Antifungal and antibacterial properties
- c. Topical application for skin infections
- d. Oral medication for systemic infections

Chemical Source:

A. Antifungal agents like:

- a. Clotrimazole
- b. Miconazole
- c. Terbinafine
- d. Griseofulvin

Biological Name:

- a. *Trichophyton rubrum* (most common causative agent)

Chemical Source:

1. Catechins (polyphenolic compounds)
2. Caffeine
3. L-Theanine (an amino acid)
4. Volatile oils like hexenal and hexenol

Biological Name: *Camellia sinensis* (Tea plant)

Morphology:

1. Evergreen shrub or small tree
2. Dark green, elliptical leaves with a pointed tip
3. Small, white, fragrant flowers
4. Fruits are small, capsular, and contain seeds

Uses:

1. Beverage: Consumed as a refreshing, low-caffeine drink
2. Medicinal:
 - a. Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties
 - b. Cardiovascular health and cholesterol management
 - c. Anti-cancer properties
 - d. Immune system support

- b. Other species: *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Epidermophyton floccosum*, *Microsporum canis*

Morphology:

- a. Fungal hyphae (branching filaments) in the skin
- b. Circular, ring-like lesions with clear centers
- c. Red, itchy, and scaly skin around the lesions
- d. Fungal spores (conidia) in the skin and environment

Green Tea:

3. Cosmetic:

1. Skincare products for antioxidant and anti-aging benefits
 2. Haircare products for scalp health and shine
4. Culinary:

- a. Ingredient in various recipes, like smoothies and baked goods

5. Traditional Medicine:

- a. Used in Ayurvedic and Chinese medicine for centuries

Aloe Vera:

Biological Name:

- a. Aloe barbadensis Miller (most commonly used species)
- b. Other species: Aloe vera Linne, Aloe pernyi, Aloe ferox

Chemical Source:

- a. Aloin (anthraquinone compound)
- b. Aloe-emodin (anthraquinone compound)
- c. Vitamins A, C, and E
- d. Minerals like calcium, potassium, and magnesium
- e. Amino acids like lysine, threonine, and alanine
- f. Polysaccharides like acemannan and aloeride

Uses:

1. Skin and Hair Care:

- a. Soothes burns, wounds, and skin irritations
- b. Hydrates and moisturizes skin and hair
- c. Treats acne, eczema, and psoriasis

2. Medicinal:

- a. Treats constipation and digestive issues
- b. Lowers blood sugar levels
- c. Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties

3. Oral Health:

- a. Soothes mouth sores and gum inflammation
- b. Reduces plaque and prevents tooth decay

4. Food and Beverages:

- a. Used as a natural remedy in juices and smoothies
- b. Added to food products for nutritional benefits

5. Cosmetic:

- a. Ingredient in skincare and haircare products
- b. Used in sunscreens and after-sun products

Acne:

Biological Name:

- a. No specific biological name, as acne is a skin condition
- b. However, the bacteria that can cause acne is Propionibacterium acnes (P. acnes)

Chemical Source:

- a. Excess sebum production
- b. Dead skin cells
- c. Bacterial growth (P. acnes)

d. Inflammation and oxidative stress

Uses:

A. Acne is not a substance with uses, but rather a skin condition that requires treatment

B. Treatments include:

- 1. Topical creams and gels (benzoyl peroxide, salicylic acid, retinoids)
- 2. Oral antibiotics and retinoids
- 3. Hormonal therapies
- 4. Blue light therapy

Morphology:

- a. Acne lesions:
- b. Comedones (blackheads and whiteheads)
- c. Papules (pink bumps)
- d. Pustules (pus-filled bumps)
- e. Nodules (large, painful bumps)
- f. Cysts (large, painful bumps with pus)

Skin characteristics:

- a. Excess oil production
- b. Clogged pores
- c. Inflammation and redness

Skincare Requirement

1. Proper skin care is essential for maintaining healthy, radiant skin. While individual needs vary based on factors like skin type, age, and environmental factors, there are several fundamental requirements that apply to most people.

2. Cleansing: Cleansing the skin twice daily is crucial to remove dirt, oil, and impurities that accumulate throughout the day and night. Use a gentle, pH-balanced cleanser appropriate for your skin type to avoid stripping away natural oils.

Exfoliation: Regular exfoliation helps to slough off dead skin cells, preventing clogged pores and promoting cell turnover. Choose a chemical or physical exfoliant suitable for your skin's sensitivity level, and use it 1-3 times per week.

CONCLUSION

Herbal drugs have shown significant promise in the treatment of various skin disorders, offering an

alternative or complementary approach to conventional therapies. Many plant-based compounds possess anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and wound-healing properties that can help address conditions such as acne, eczema, psoriasis, dermatitis, and fungal infections. However, while the use of herbal remedies is gaining popularity, it is essential to ensure their safety and efficacy through scientific research and clinical trials. Potential side effects, drug interactions, and the quality of herbal products should be carefully considered. Ultimately, the integration of herbal drugs into skincare regimens should be done under the guidance of healthcare professionals, ensuring a balanced and informed approach to treatment.

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HOW TO CITE: Gayatri Dalvi*, Vishakha Shinde, Shinde Trupti, Swapnil Kale, Sneha Kanase, Divya Gore, A Review of Herbal Drugs Used in The Treatment of Skin Disorder, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 12, 2248-2256. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14499152>